

ZOOMORPHIC VIEW OF THE UNIVERSE

Juraeva Barno Nizomiddinovna

A teacher of Termez State University

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ABSTRACT

Zoomorphism is the converse of this: it is the attribution of animal-like mental states to humans. Zoomorphism proceeds by first understanding what kind of mental states animals have and then attributing these mental states to humans. Anthropomorphism is the methodology of attributing human-like mental states to animals. Zoomorphism has been widely used as scientific methodology especially in cognitive neuroscience. But it has not been taken seriously as a philosophical explanatory paradigm: as a way of explaining the building blocks of the human mind. The philosophical explanatory paradigm of zoomorphism may not explain all aspects of human behavior (although it may explain surprisingly many), but if we accept the zoomorphic way of thinking about the human mind, we should only posit new, different kinds of mental states if the zoomorphic attribution of animal mental states fails to explain our behavior. In this article discussed those main information and methods about zoomorphic view of the universe.

Anthropomorphism and Zoomorphism. Anthropomorphism is the methodology of attributing human-like mental states to animals: when it comes to explaining the minds of non-human animals, we can and should make reference to mental states that we are familiar with from our understanding of the human mind. The merits and demerits of anthropomorphism have been heavily contested in recent times, but I want to bracket these debates for the purposes of this paper. I want to make a distinction between zoomorphism as scientific methodology and zoomorphism as

philosophical explanatory paradigm. A similar distinction can be made about anthropomorphism as well, so I will introduce this distinction in this more familiar context. Anthropomorphism, the attribution of human-like mental states to animals can be used as a piece of scientific methodology: when explaining some specific behavior of a certain kind of animals, we should attribute certain mental states to them that we know from human psychology. But anthropomorphism is not merely a piece of scientific methodology, it is also a philosophical explanatory paradigm, according to which we arrive at

the correct way of understanding animal minds if we start by postulating that these animals have human-like mental states.

Anthropomorphism as scientific methodology aims to describe the specific mental states of a certain species. Anthropomorphism as philosophical explanatory paradigm, in contrast, is a very general theoretical assumption about how animal minds should and could be explained. Here is an example: We know (somehow) that we humans have beliefs. So it is permissible to describe the behavior of animals in terms of beliefs. This is anthropomorphism as philosophical explanatory paradigm. Now, just what beliefs one attributes to an animal is a task for anthropomorphism as scientific methodology. One can take anthropomorphism to be a useful piece of scientific methodology in some contexts without endorsing anthropomorphism as philosophical explanatory paradigm. And one can endorse anthropomorphism as philosophical explanatory paradigm without having any interest whatsoever in what kinds of mental states one needs to postulate to explain specific animal behavior. But anthropomorphism as philosophical explanatory paradigm is the theoretical foundation and regulative ideal of anthropomorphism as scientific methodology.

Some progress might be made in the anthropomorphism literature if we paid attention to this distinction, but that is not the aim of this paper. It's time to return to zoomorphism. A similar distinction could be made between zoomorphism as scientific methodology and zoomorphism as philosophical explanatory paradigm. Zoomorphism as philosophical explanatory paradigm is a general theoretical

assumption about how we can explain the human mind and its building blocks. It asserts that we should only posit mental state types that we know from the study of animal cognition.

Zoomorphism as scientific methodology, in contrast, is a tool for understanding what specific mental states we, humans, have, on the basis of postulating animal-like mental states. As before, one can use zoomorphism as scientific methodology (maybe because a certain experiment would be too intrusive to undertake in humans, but not in animals) without endorsing zoomorphism as philosophical explanatory paradigm. And one can endorse zoomorphism as philosophical explanatory paradigm without doing so in order to be able to use zoomorphic scientific methodology. Nonetheless, zoomorphism as philosophical explanatory paradigm is the theoretical foundation and regulative ideal of zoomorphism as scientific methodology. In the next section, I argue that as scientific methodology, zoomorphism has been widely used and it has been immensely successful. The focus of the rest of the paper is zoomorphism as philosophical explanatory paradigm.

The aim of this section is to show how zoomorphism as scientific methodology works. The first thing we should notice is that the general explanatory scheme zoomorphism uses, namely, to import some considerations about animals to explain humans has been very widespread, starting from anatomical studies of animals in order to understand human anatomy. But the focus of this paper is zoomorphism as a way of understanding the human mind. And using considerations about the mind of nonhuman animals when explaining the human mind is an equally widespread and

equally successful research methodology, at least in some branches of cognitive science, especially cognitive neuroscience. An important example of how the scientific methodology of zoomorphism can be used to illuminate how the human mind works is the literature on mirror neurons.

Mirror neurons are not mental states. But the zoomorphic attribution of this anatomical feature (that we know from animals) to humans nonetheless can help us to understand the human mind better. The mirror neuron system (or, rather, systems) consists of bi-modal neurons that get activated both when the agent performs an action and when she perceives another agent performing this action. And here the literature on mirror neurons can give us some guidance about how the methodology of zoomorphism can and should be used. Importantly, it does not follow from the methodology of zoomorphism that we should conclude on the basis of having found a mechanism in nonhuman animals that humans also have this very mechanism—it is a dubious inference that it follows from the single cell recordings in the rhesus monkey brain that the human brain works the same way. It is very important to emphasize that zoomorphism is not supposed to give us a full description of the human mind: it is an explanatory paradigm for finding out about the human mind but there is no reason to believe that it is the ultimate or the only tool we have for understanding the human mind. A comparison with anthropomorphism may be useful to elucidate this point.

Zoomorphism and Behaviorism. Another important thing to clarify about zoomorphism is that it does not entail behaviorism—another old and influential

philosophical explanatory paradigm. Zoomorphism is very much in the business of attributing mental states both to nonhuman animals and to humans—in fact, the main claim is that we should do the latter on the basis of the former. Behaviorism denies that any such attribution of mental states would be justified. Behaviorism could be considered to be an extreme limiting case of zoomorphism: the idea would be that as we should not attribute any mental state to animals, we should not attribute any mental state to humans either.

The comparison between zoomorphism and behaviorism is important in as much as it highlights how much the explanatory scheme of zoomorphism is determined by what we take to be those mental states that we are justified to attribute to nonhuman animals. If you are behaviorist, the answer to this would be no mental states. But the aim of cognitive ethology and comparative psychology is to provide plausible candidates for mental states that we are justified to attribute to nonhuman animals. And then we can use these considerations to justify the attribution of these very mental states to humans.

I argued for a philosophical explanatory paradigm of attributing mental states of animals to humans. But this obviously raises the question how we know what mental states animals have. So one could worry that all zoomorphism achieved was to shift the problem from humans to non-human animals. If we want to substantiate zoomorphism as a philosophical explanatory paradigm, we need to ask what mental states we should attribute to animals (which, in turn, we also attribute to humans). I will come back to the problem of how zoomorphism as a

philosophical explanatory paradigm about the human mind relies on some other philosophical explanatory paradigm about the animal mind in Sect. But there is another issue that needs to be addressed. On the other hand, we can do more intrusive experiments on animals that are further away from us in terms of homology. We have a form of trade-off between using findings from animals close to us in homology and animals easier to experiment on.

Zoomorphism as a philosophical explanatory paradigm can be implemented as scientific methodology in a variety of ways. Depending on how we do so, we may get very different answers to the question about which animals we should use as the explanatory basis of human mental states. Nonetheless, an important part of zoomorphism as a philosophical explanatory paradigm (and not as scientific methodology) that as a general rule, it should not be assumed that closeness in terms of homology always wins out (for example, nothing would rule out that the reason for the similarity of behavior is not homology but analogy). In this section, I was hoping to show that zoomorphism is not a particularly radical explanatory paradigm. Crucially, it does not have any

claims to exclusivity when it comes to understanding the human mind: we should use zoomorphism as the first step of understanding the human mind, but a lot needs to be done after this first step is completed.

Animals perform actions: they run away from predators and approach prey, for example. And they do so successfully most of the time. Thus, we have very strong reason to attribute motor representations to them. But then if we apply the explanatory scheme of zoomorphism, the first step of understanding the human behavior would be to explain it in terms of our motor representations. This approach, of course, has its limits. While many of our fine-grained bodily movements may be explained by virtue of attributing motor representations, some aspects of human cognition (especially linguistic or rational reasoning) clearly can't be. But if we want to follow the explanatory paradigm of zoomorphism, then we first need to see how far we can go in our understanding of the human mind by using motor representations and we can only use different mental states when the human behavior is clearly not possible to fully describe only with the help of motor representations.

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